

All Patient Cases (images and clinical data) collected until 23/04/2024 in the CHAIMELEON Repository related to Lung cancer.

ID: 822ad0bd-02d1-4932-a8b2-7d5679c3d4f0

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/822ad0bd-02d1-4932-a8b2-7d5679c3d4f0/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 3140

Subjects count: 1254

Age range: Between 29 years and 91 years

Sex: Male, Female, Unkown

Body part(s): CHEST, ABDOMEN, SPINE, NECK, BRAIN, HEAD, LUNG, WHOLEBODY, THORAX, THORAX / ABDOMEN, THORAX INJECTE, TAP, SERVICE, EXTREMITY, CRANE, LSPINE, CSPINE, TAP IV, TORAX, UNKNOWN, COU THORAX, HEART, TC TOTAL BODY, TOTAL BODY, ABDO PELVIS, ABDOPELV, PORT SHOULDER, TDM ABDOMEN / PE, SINUS CTAP, CTAP, RACHIS, TDM THORAX / ABD, THORAX IV, TB COLLO, Unknown

Modality: CT, PT, DX, CR